

The role of the surface acidic/basic centers and redox sites on TiO₂ in the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction

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Figure S2. Effect of chemisorption temperature on the NH₃-TPD curves of TiO₂ (a), total acid sites concentration (error bars $\pm 2\%$) (b), and CO₂-TPD curve (c).

Figure S2a shows the NH₃-TPD curves of a calcined TiO₂ (PC500) sample obtained at different NH₃ chemisorption temperatures. Here, it is clear that the NH₃-TPD curves are undoubtedly dependent on the temperature, but all present a broad desorption peak with a maximum desorption increasing with temperature at 110, 165 and 220 °C, respectively. TPD peaks in the region above 400 °C are related to strong Brønsted and Lewis type acid sites, the peaks appearing between 400 and 177 °C can be attributed to the desorption of NH₃ from intermediate acid sites, while the peaks in the region below 177 °C are associated with NH₃ desorption from weak acid sites.[1] Therefore, the NH₃-TPD curve of TiO₂ recorded at the reaction temperature (i.e. 50 °C) reveals that this sample mainly contains weak acid sites.[1,2] Figure S2b evidences how the total acidity of this sample decreases linearly with the chemisorption temperature, obtaining overall acidity values at 50, 100 and 150°C of 0.85, 0.62 and 0.42 mmol g⁻¹, respectively.

The CO₂-TPD curve of TiO₂ (Figure S2c) reveals an overall basicity of 0.37 mmol g⁻¹. This curve exhibits three different desorption peaks at about 90 °C, 185 °C and a broad band at 290–550 °C. The small peak at about 90 °C is ascribed to the desorption of CO₂ from weak base sites. The predominant peak at 185 °C is related to the presence of

intermediate base sites, while the broad band above 400 °C can be attributed to the desorption of CO₂ from strong Brønsted- and Lewis-type base sites.[1–3] Consequently, TiO₂ (PC500) sample mainly contains intermediate basic sites under our experimental conditions.

Fig. S3. TGA-MS analysis of a fresh (a) and calcined (b) TiO₂ sample under 50 ml min⁻¹ air flow and Ar flow (c).

Humidity and carbon content of a fresh and calcined TiO₂ sample was studied by TGA using a heating program of 10 °C/min up to 1200 °C under 50 ml min⁻¹ air flow. Evolved gases from the TGA were fed to a MS, which recorded H₂O and CO₂ signals.

TG-MS results indicate that a fresh TiO₂ sample undergoes a weight loss of 9.4 wt.% up to 400 °C due to the elimination of adsorbed water and organic residues. Above 400 °C, TiO₂ shows an additional weight loss of 1.3 wt.%, which is associated to the elimination of hydroxyl groups and lattice oxygen, but also to the thermal decomposition of inorganic carbon species (note increase in m/z = 44 signal).

After calcination at 400 °C (Fig. S3b), the weight loss up to this temperature (ca. 2.3 wt.%) is ascribed to the elimination of water and CO₂, adsorbed over TiO₂ surface upon the exposure to air. This weight loss is 4-times lower than that of the fresh sample. Above 400 °C, the sample undergoes a weight loss of 1.1 wt.%, slightly lower than that of fresh sample (1.3 wt.%). This is associated with the thermal decomposition of adsorbed inorganic carbon species and the elimination of hydroxyl groups and lattice oxygen (650 – 850°C) due to a thermal reduction of TiO₂.

TG-MS measurements under Ar flow (Fig. S3c) shows a weight loss of ca. 2 wt.% at low temperatures (< 400°C), which is associated with the decomposition of organic residues and the desorption of CO₂ and H₂O from TiO₂ surface (note the increase in CO₂ and H₂O MS signals). The oxygen peak at ca. 700 °C is attributed to a loss of hydroxyl groups and lattice oxygen from TiO₂ due to a partial reduction of the sample. Finally, the evolution of CO₂ (m/z=44) above 1000 °C is associated with the decomposition of carbonate-like species. This results agrees well with TG-MS measurements conducted under air flow before calcination (Fig. S3a).

Fig. S4. NAP-XPS C 1s spectra recorded for TiO₂ under UHV in dark conditions (a) and exposed to UV illumination (365 nm) (b).

Fig. S5. NAP-XPS O 1s spectra recorded for TiO₂ under UHV in dark conditions (a) and exposed to UV illumination (365 nm) (b).

TiO₂ surface exhibits three main components (Fig. S5a); the major contribution located at 529.4 eV is attributed to bulk oxygen from Ti-O bonds in the TiO₂ crystal lattice, while the peaks at 530.5 eV and 531.4 eV correspond to bridging oxygen (O_B) and surface hydroxyl oxygen (O_{OH}), respectively. The additional contribution at 532.4 eV is assigned to physisorbed water molecules (H₂O_{phys.}) in the upper hydration layer.[4,5] UV illumination (Fig. S5b) leads to a loss of physisorbed water molecules and an increase in the amount of surface OH groups.[6] Both observations suggest a photoinduced decomposition of water adsorbed on TiO₂ surface (see Table S6).

Fig. S6. TiO₂ selectivity (bars, left axis) and carbon products yield (dots, right axes) under UV irradiation ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 365 \text{ nm}$) and different reaction atmospheres: CO₂-H₂O, Ar-H₂O, dry Ar and dry CO₂ (a); TiO₂ pretreatment with Ar+H₂O atmosphere under UV illumination followed by a CO₂-H₂O reaction (b); In situ DRIFTS experiments under Ar+H₂O atmosphere in the dark (grey) and under UV illumination (red) (c).

Fig. S6a shows a fast decrease on the overall carbon products yield under all reaction atmospheres different than CO₂+H₂O. Fig. S6b shows that the production yield of TiO₂ after a humid argon pretreatment only reaches less than 10% of the original values. In situ DRIFT experiments under Ar+H₂O atmosphere (Fig. S6c) show an increase of the signals associated to water, bicarbonates and hydroxycarbonates, together with a decrease of carbonates. In contrast, UV illumination conduces to an opposite behaviour, leading to the formation of b-CO₃²⁻ and m-CO₃²⁻ species (assignments details in Table S6).

Fig. S7. Product evolution over TiO_2 under dry (a) and humid (b) Ar atmosphere, using a hydrocarbon standard gas mixture (containing 100 ppm of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, methane, ethane, ethylene, propane and butane) as feeding flow and UV illumination ($\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$). Error bars $\pm 5\%$.

Fig. S8. In-situ Raman spectra of TiO₂ under CO₂ + H₂O atmosphere in the dark and under UV illumination ($\lambda = 365$ nm) (a); Post-reaction Raman spectra of a catalyst filter (b); yellowish colored spots on a catalyst filter after reaction, ascribed to the formation of surface peroxy- and peroxocarbonate species (c).

Fig. S9. In-situ NAP-XPS O 1s spectra recorded for TiO₂ under UHV (I); after dosing CO₂ and H₂O at P = 4.375·10⁻² and 6.250 10⁻³ mbar, respectively (II); and under UV illumination (365 nm) in CO₂ and H₂O atmosphere (III) (a); Magnification from squared region in Fig. S9a (b).

Fig. S10. ^1H MAS NMR spectra of TiO_2 exposed to $^{13}\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ atmosphere in the dark and under prolonged UV illumination (**left**). MD Simulations of the interaction between H_2O , CO_2 , Surface hydroxyl groups, bicarbonate and carbonate species over the surface of a TiO_2 nanoparticle (4 nm). Dashed blue lines represent hydrogen-bridge bonding (**right**). Titanium (gray), oxygen (red), carbon (light grey), and hydrogen (white).

The ^1H MAS NMR spectra shows 4 signals attributed to (i) terminal hydroxyl OH_T groups (1.3 ppm), (ii) adsorbed H_2O (5.2 ppm) forming hydrated OH through hydrogen-bonding interaction, (iii) bridging hydroxyl OH_B groups (6.9 ppm) and (iv) hydrogencarbonate (11.2 ppm) formed by the interaction of H_2O or OH with CO_2 [7] UV illumination conduces to the depletion of OH_T groups, and a slight decrease of OH_B and adsorbed H_2O . The small contribution at ca. 3-5 ppm region is tentatively assigned to CH_3 or CH_3O^- intermediates, which disappear after 20 h under reaction. The broadening in this signal can be also attributed to the presence of peroxides.

Fig. S11. In situ DRIFTS experiments over TiO_2 recorded under $\text{CO}_2+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the dark (blue) and UV illumination (red) (a), and Ar (b) atmosphere in the dark (grey) and UV illumination (red).

Fig. 11a shows an increase in ν_{OH} associated to hydroxyl groups, H_2O , bicarbonates and hydroxycarbonates, which decrease under UV illumination. Fig. S11b exhibits a depletion of ν_{OH} signals upon flushing TiO_2 surface with an Argon flow at 50°C . This behaviour significantly accentuates under UV illumination. Specifically, the right-hand side Figure S11b shows a depletion of the OH stretching region (ca. $1600 - 1750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which includes hydroxyl groups without H-bonding interaction coming from water, TiO_2 surface and/or bicarbonate species[8,9]. In addition, there is a depletion of $m\text{-CO}_3^{2-}$ (ca. $1410 - 1440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and HCO_3^- species (ca. $1200 - 1210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) that is accompanied by an increase in $b\text{-CO}_3^{2-}$ and CO_2^- species (ca. $1230 - 1330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (details of assignments in Table S6).

Fig. S12. ^{13}C CP/MAS spectra with proton decoupling (a) and $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ static NMR (b) of TiO_2 after the following treatment: 5 h at 150 °C under vacuum; exposed to $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ at P = 1.45 bar and moist; and exposed to $^{13}\text{CO}_2$, moist and UV irradiation (365 nm) during 6 h (from bottom to top).

Fig. S13. ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR spectra with proton decoupling corresponding to TiO_2 after the following treatment: 5 h at 150°C under vacuum (I) and exposed to $^{13}\text{CO}_2$, moist and UV irradiation (365 nm) during 2 and 10 h (II and III, respectively). Spectra IV and V were recorded after 7 and 33 days elapsed reaction (a); NAP-XPS C 1s spectra acquired after ceasing the illumination and evacuating the gases from the analysis chamber (b).

Fig. S14. Main adsorption configurations and conversion pathways of reactants and primary intermediates in CO₂ photoreduction. Atom colors: blue for Ti, red for O, grey for C and white for H.

Fig. S15. O₂ and CO₂ evolution over a TiO₂ sample exposed to UV irradiation ($\lambda_{\max} = 365$ nm) and Ar-H₂O (a) or Ar (b) atmosphere. Error bars $\pm 5\%$.

Argon and Ar-H₂O reactions were performed to understand the contribution of surface carbon residues (observed by XPS, chemical analysis and TG experiments) in the product quantification. Besides the products summarized in Table S3, we observed the presence of CO₂ and O₂. In the case of CO₂ evolution, the experiments performed under Argon atmosphere exhibited an amount of 220.9 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹, which is equivalent to 0.9 mg of carbon. This value is 9 times higher than that obtained by elemental analysis (<

0.1 mg), indicating that this signal is mainly due to adsorbed CO₂ or surface carbonate/bicarbonate decomposition.

On the other hand, the CO₂ evolution in the presence of water increased to 481.9 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹, which is equivalent to 1.96 mg of carbon. This value is approximately 20 times higher than the obtained by elemental analysis (< 0.1 mg). Similarly, to the reaction in Argon, this CO₂ evolution is attributed to adsorbed CO₂ or surface carbonate/bicarbonate decomposition, which is enhanced by the presence of water.

In the case of the O₂ evolution, we observed that even using high purity reagents (CO₂ and H₂O) and a well-sealed reactor some air is inevitably introduced in the reaction system (c.a. less than 100 ppm in all cases, probably coming from the reagents (e.g. dissolved in water)), even after the vacuum treatment. These traces are visible in Fig. S15 as the initial O₂ value at t=0 h, at which UV illumination has not started yet. Besides, O₂ traces are also shown in Fig. S16, where we depicted the evolution of the N₂:O₂ ratios in our experiments under different reaction atmospheres, evidencing that the oxygen is coming from air (i.e. reagents and ambient exposure).

Fig. S16. Evolution of $O_2:N_2$ ratios during the photocatalytic experiments performed under the following reaction atmospheres: Ar (a), CO_2 (b), CO_2-H_2O (c), and Ar- H_2O (d). Error bars $\pm 5\%$.

Fig. S17. Acid washing regeneration study: Comparison of initial TiO₂ photoactivity (left) vs product evolution after a regeneration (R) with acid washing. For the acid treatment, catalyst filters were immersed in diluted acid solutions (0.1M aqueous HNO₃) for 30 min, rinsed with deionized water, dried at 100°C and tested in reaction under identical conditions. Error bars \pm 5%.

Table S1. Comparison of gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction studies on TiO₂ under UV illumination.

Catalyst	Operation mode	Electron donor	Product evolution rate (μmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)			Reference
			CO	H ₂	CH ₄	
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	25.5	7.6	0.9	This study
TiO ₂ ^a	Batch	H ₂ O vapor	-	-	<0.1	[10]
TiO ₂ ^a	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	9.9	-	-	[11]
TiO ₂ ^{a,b}	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	8653.8	-	1153.8	[12]
TiO ₂ ^b	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	1.5	0.0	2.0	[13]
TiO ₂ ^c	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	4.0	0.0	0.3	[14]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	11.1	7.5	2.0	[15]
TiO ₂ ^d	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	1.4	-	0.1	[16]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	15.3	5.6	1.1	[17]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	5	-	0.5	[18]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	9.4	2.6	0.4	[19]
TiO ₂ ^e	Batch	H ₂	43.0	0.0	9.0	[20]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂	16.7	-	8.3	[21]
TiO ₂ ^f	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	4.8	-	0.8	[22]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	2.0	-	0.5	[23]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	0.7	-	0.1	[24]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	-	-	0.3	[25]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	45.0	-	37.5	[26]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	0.2	0.2	0.2	[27]
TiO ₂	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	1.3	-	-	[28]
TiO ₂ ^g	Continuous	H ₂ O vapor	6.3	-	147.2	[29]
TiO ₂	Batch	H ₂ O vapor	2.7	3.0	0.2	[30]

^a Study highlighted with a red dot in Figure 1a; ^b mesoporous TiO₂; ^c Ultrathin; ^d mesoporous single crystals; ^e nanowires; ^f Black TiO₂; ^g Nanosheet.

Table S2. Summary of operating parameters and photonic efficiencies (ξ) included in this work and in reported photocatalytic CO₂ reduction literature with TiO₂.

Operation mode	Photonic efficiency, ξ (%)					Reference
	H ₂	CO	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₄	C ₂ H ₆	
Gas	0.06	0.21	0.03			This work
Gas	1 ^e					[17]
Gas		0.14				[19]
Gas		<0.01 ^b				[20]
Gas	0.05	0.16	<0.01 ^c			[25]
Gas	1 ^e					[30]
Gas	0.13 ^b					[31]
Gas			0.07 ^b			[32]
Gas		0.04				[33]
Gas		<0.01 ^a				[34]
Gas		<0.01 ^b				[35]
Gas		<0.01 ^d				[36]
Gas			<0.01 ^d			[37]
Liquid			0.34 ^a			[38]
Liquid	0.43 ^a	0.27 ^a	1.89 ^a	0.04 ^a	1.89 ^a	[39]
Liquid	0.14 ^a	0.04 ^a	0.24 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.24 ^a	[39]
Liquid	0.02 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.13 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.13 ^a	[39]

^a Apparent Quantum Efficiency (AQE); ^b Quantum Yield (QY); ^c Formal Quantum Efficiency (FQE); ^d Quantum Efficiency (QE); ^e Quantum Yield Index (QYI).

Table S3. Cumulative production ($\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$) over TiO_2 after 15 h of UV irradiation ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 365 \text{ nm}$) under different reaction atmospheres: $\text{CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, CO_2 , $\text{Ar-H}_2\text{O}$ and Ar .

Reaction atmosphere	CO_2	H_2	CO	CH_4	CH_3OH	C_2H_6
$\text{CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$	-	78.9	254.8	5.9	9.8	0.4
CO_2	-	1.0	21.8	43.5	0.0	2.9
$\text{Ar-H}_2\text{O}$	481.9	39.3	158.9	7.2	3.4	0.7
Ar	220.9	0.4	8.7	19.4	0.0	0.6

Table S4. NAP-XPS C 1s data collected on TiO₂ sample under UHV conditions and UV irradiation (365 nm).

Component	UHV			UHV + UV		
	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)
C-C	284.1	1.3	41.0	284.2	1.2	63.1
C-O	285.5	1.3	34.4	285.1	1.2	22.1
C=O/COO⁻	286.8	1.3	14.2	286.3	1.2	8.2
CO₃²⁻	288.1	1.2	8.9	288.7	1.2	3.8
HCO₃⁻	289.2	1.3	1.5	288.9	1.2	2.8

Table S5. NAP-XPS O 1s data collected on TiO₂ sample under UHV conditions and UV irradiation (365 nm).

Component	UHV			UHV + UV		
	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)
O-Ti	529.4	1.0	80.4	529.4	1.1	80.3
O _B	530.5	1.2	12.4	530.5	1.1	12.4
O _H	531.4	1.1	5.0	531.3	1.0	5.6
H ₂ O _{phys.}	532.4	1.2	2.2	532.5	1.2	1.7

Table S6. Band assignments for the infrared spectra of TiO₂. Superscripts refer to literature studies, which are listed in the References Section (Supporting Information). Not specified IR vibration modes are referred as N/A. Raman shifts of surface species are also listed.

Vibrational bands of species adsorbed on TiO ₂ (1900 cm ⁻¹ to 700 cm ⁻¹)			
Compound	Vibration	IR bands (cm ⁻¹)	Raman shifts (cm ⁻¹)
Water, H ₂ O	δ HOH	1600[40], 1630[41], 1400-1650 (gas)[42]	
	scissor-bending	1620[43], 1624[44], 1630[45], 1635[46], 1637-1639[28,47,48], 1640-1650[49-53]	
Carbon dioxide, CO ₂ , free (or weakly bonded)	ν _s	1379[54]	
	2ν ₂ overtone (Fermi resonance)	1268 (split at 1271, 1260)[54]	1280[55], 1285[56], 1380[55], 1388[56]
	degenerate deformation	667[56]	
Carboxylate, CO ₂ ⁻	N/A	1200-1700[50], 1210[57], 1245[58], 1247[52], 1248[48,59,60], 1250[28,61], 1252[62], 1267[49], 1312[54,63], 1319[47], 1355[64], 1361[65], 1529[47], 1569[64], 1587[64], 1626[65], 1650[57], 1662[65], 1663[57], 1664[66], 1668[54,62,63], 1670[52,61,67], 1672[58,60], 1673[28,48,68]	
	ν _{as} CO	1513[29], 1670[50], 1723[29], 1750[54], 1773[54], 1700-1900[56]	
	ν _s CO	1100-1200[54,56], 1220[29], 1250[50], 1254[69], 1258[29]	
Carbon monoxide, CO (adsorbed)	N/A	1495[52], 1853[47]	
Bidentate carbonate, b-CO ₃ ²⁻	N/A	1055[70], 1059[60,61], 1230[44], 1275[47], 1319[63,71], 1323[67], 1340[62,65,72], 1343[48], 1344[58], 1345[52], 1347[73], 1348[48], 1360[28,67], 1361[65], 1376[66], 1411[44], 1479[44], 1500-1590[52], 1545[72], 1053[74], 1555[48], 1570[48], 1578[58], 1579[63], 1583[52], 1586[60], 1594[62], 1596[73], 1597[67], 1621[66], 1626[65], 1637[71], 1639[64], 1666[71]	

	$v_{as} CO$	1105[75], 1125[75], 1349[57], 1363[57], 1364[61], 1378[61], 1415[50], 1555[48], 1566[50], 1570[28], 1579[63], 1580[56,61], 1589[70], 1600[76], 1605[69], 1670[56], 1672[74], 1802[75]	(1350, 1410)[77], 1608[78]
	$v_s CO$	1243[56,74], 1278[61], 1315[70], 1319[63], 1320[56,61], 1342[69], 1348[48], 1355[50], 1360[28]	1045[78], 1067[55], 1313[78]
	$v_B OCO$	610[75]	
Monodentate carbonate, $m-CO_3^{2-}$	N/A	1294[44], 1300[28], 1377[61], 1385[73], 1386[62], 1461[63], 1467[67], 1486[48], 1500-1590[52,67], 1503[48], 1512[73], 1540[28]	
	$v_{as} CO$	1321[61], 1378[75], 1409[57], 1415[50], 1419[57], 1510[50,69], 1518[66], 1510-1560[65], 1540[28], 1565[66], 1578[74], 1584[75], 1575-1590[56], 1576[75], 1595[74]	(1350, 1410)[77], 1576[78]
	$v_s CO$	1058[75], 1300[28], 1315[74], 1359[74], 1363[79], 1320-1370[56], 1377[70], 1392[50,69], 1394[80]	1067[55], 1284[78]
Bicarbonate, HCO_3^-	N/A	1203[61], 1220[28,47,58,61,70], 1221[52], 1222[50,66], 1235[62], 1389[71], 1406[65], 1411[58], 1413[81], 1415[52], 1416[70], 1418[11,72], 1420-1428[28,50,52], 1424[61,66], 1436-1464[62], 1447-1464[71,73], 1481[57,61], 1599[47], 1623[50,61], 1660[44], 1663[57,81], 1672[11,72], 1683[71], 1687[71]	
Bidentate bicarbonate, $b-HCO_3^-$	$v_{as} CO$	1426[75], 1448[75], 1497[75], 1505[75], 1574[75], 1613[75], 1625[75]	(1556, 1648)[78]
	$v_s CO$	1048[75], 1052[75], 1063[75], 1068[75], 1117[75]	1360[55], 1445[78]
	$v COH$		1015[55]
	$v_B OCO$	645[75], 664[75], 670[75], 713[75]	
	$v_B COH$	1193[75], 1207[75], 1212[75], 1218[75], 1230[75]	1302[55]
Monodentate bicarbonate, $m-HCO_3^-$	$v_{as} CO$	1432[75], 1555[56,82], 1555-1580[56], 1630[74], 1656[75], 1670[82]	(1556, 1648)[78]

	v_s CO	1052[75], 1340[82], 1408[74], 1412[48], 1420[28,56,82], 1430[74], 1434[70], 1425- 1443[56]	1360[55], 1445[78]
	v COH		1015[55]
	v_B OCO	664[75]	
	v_B COH	1207[75]	1302[55]
	δ OH	1215[40], 1220[28,56,82], 1221[74], 1222[70], 1223[48], 1215-1227[79]	1232[78]
Formic acid, HCOOH	N/A	1379[52], 1618[83], 1716[52]	
	v C=O	1670[42], 1665[84], 1675[42], 1676[85], 1725[42,61]	
	v C-O or δ C-H	1277[85], 1278[42], 1332[42], 1380[84], 1728[84]	
Formate, HCOO⁻	N/A	1340[45], 1355[71], 1359[64,86], 1360[87,88], 1363[89], 1368[64], 1372[45], 1379[88], 1380[86], 1381[89], 1395[45], 1396[71], 1455[45], 1458[71], 1540[45], 1541[71], 1552[89], 1555[88], 1558[45,64], 1565[64], 1567[86], 1571[67], 1590[87], 1592[45], 1605[29], 1616[71], 1649[45], 1700[45], 1825[45], 1844[45], 1868[45], 2212[29]	(1370, 1392, 1567, 1720)[90]
Bidentate formate, b-HCOO⁻	v_{as} COO	1537[42], 1550[84], 1552[42,85], 1555[63], 1560[40,42,91,92], 1580[56], 1582[93], 1585[87], 1590 ¹¹	
	C-H def. or CO ₂ rocking	1385[93], 1386[42], 1400[91], 1412[42]	
	v_s COO	1341[93], 1350[91], 1357[87], 1359[42], 1360[92], 1365[40,56], 1370[42,63,84], 1377[85], 1388[41]	
	v C-O	1277[85], 1279[85]	
Formaldehyde, H₂CO	N/A	1080[87], 1106[83], 1107[80], 1116[87], 1249[45], 1270[94], 1357[53], 1414[53], 1418[45], 1444[87], 1509[80], 1551[53], 1604[87], 1715[45], 1745[80], 1749[45], 1770[45]	
	v C=O	1429[84], 1744[84] (gas phase)	
	v CH ₂ =O	1727[84], 1739[79], 1745[42]	
	δ CH ₂	1412[95], 1452[95], 1485[84], 1502[84]	
Methanol, CH₃OH	CH ₃ deformation mode	1467[96]	

	H-O-C deformation	1290[96,97], 1305[96], 1315[96,97], 1338[97]	
	ν C-O	(905,944)[98], 1020[98], 1030[87], 1032 (gas phase)[42], 1035[96,97], 1068[96], 1074[96,97], 1117[87], 1160[96,97]	
	δ_{as} CH ₃	1450[87]	
	δ_s CH ₃ + δ OH	1420[87]	
Methoxy, CH₃O⁻	N/A	1045[29,89], 1048[86], 1053[83], 1126[89], 1128[86], 1157[86], 1472[45], 1732[45]	
	CH ₃ deformation mode	1467[96]	
	ν C-O	1047[99], 1053[80], 1110[98], 1120[96,97], 1149[99], 1151[89], 1154[96,97]	1069[90]
	ν_{as} OCO	1567[99]	
Acetaldehyde, CH₃CHO	ν C=O	1110[87], 1680-1690[91], 1686-1729[100], 1715[87]	
	δ_{as} CH ₃	1428[87], 1434-1440[100]	
	δ CH	1370[91], 1372-1386[100]	
	δ_s CH ₃	1330[91], 1334-1355[100], 1351[87]	
	γ CH ₃ , ν C-C	1139-1110[100], 1240[91]	
Methyl formate, HCOOCH₃	ν C=O	1655[84], 1668[85], 1675 (1755 free)[42], 1727[84]	
	β -carbon formate (ν_{as} COO)	1640[101]	
	α -carbon formate (ν_{as} COO)	1530[42], 1575[101], 1588[42], 1546-1602[85]	
	α -carbon formate (C-H deformation or COO rocking)	1406[101], 1412[42]	
	β -carbon formate (ν_s COO)	1380[101], 1388[42]	
	α -carbon formate (ν_s COO)	1355[42], 1367[101], 1368[85]	
Acetate, CH₃COO⁻	ν_{as} COO	1515[91], 1530-1540[91], 1542-1546[100], 1555[82]	
	δ_{as} CH ₃	1433[41], 1450[82]	
	ν_s COO	1410[82], 1440-1445[91]	
	δ_s CH ₃	1340[82], 1350[91]	
Oxalate, C₂O₄²⁻	ν_{as} C=O	1635[93], 1680[102], 1687[93], 1711-1720[102], 1721[93]	

	v CO		(1456, 1468, 1471, 1489)[103]
	v _s C-O + v _s C-C	1409[102], 1410[93]	1392[103]
	v _s C=O + δ O-C=O	1230[102], 1240[102], 1256[93]	
	v C-C		900[103]
	δ OCO		860[103]
Peroxocarbonate or peroxodicarbonate, CO₄²⁻/C₂O₆²⁻	v O-O		(851, 860, 982)[104], 989[78]
Surface peroxy species, Ti(O₂)	N/A	928[98]	924[78]
Surface hydroperoxy species, TiOOH	v O-O	838[98]	844[78]
Surface peroxy species of a bridge type, Ti-O-O-Ti	N/A	812[98]	
Hydrogen peroxide, H₂O₂ , free (physically adsorbed)	N/A	877[98]	869[78]
Peroxide ions	v O-O		(832, 940, 1062)[104]
Superoxo-like species		1000-1200[104]	1047[104], 1130[105]

Table S7. In-situ NAP-XPS C 1s data collected on TiO₂ sample under the following conditions: UHV, CO₂ - H₂O atmosphere (P = 4.375·10⁻³ mbar), and CO₂ - H₂O atmosphere and UV irradiation (365 nm).

Component	UHV			CO ₂ + H ₂ O			CO ₂ + H ₂ O + UV		
	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)
C-Ti	-	-	-	-	-	-	282.5	1.2	6.3
C-C	284.2	1.2	31.7	284.2	1.2	24.6	284.1	1.2	21.7
C-O	285.1	1.2	25.6	285.3	1.2	26.7	285.1	1.2	21.9
C=O/COO⁻	286.2	1.1	15.3	286.7	1.2	8.1	286.8	1.2	5.9
CO₃²⁻	287.9	1.2	21.0	288.2	1.2	24.2	288.3	1.2	23.4
HCO₃⁻	289.8	1.2	6.5	289.4	1.2	16.5	289.8	1.1	2.5
CO₂^{δ-} / CO	-	-	-	-	-	-	291.1	1.0	2.4
CO₂	-	-	-	-	-	-	292.1	1.0	16.0

Table S8. In-situ NAP-XPS O 1s data collected on TiO₂ sample under the following conditions: UHV, CO₂ - H₂O atmosphere (P = 4.375·10⁻³ mbar), and CO₂ - H₂O atmosphere and UV irradiation (365 nm).

Component	UHV			CO ₂ + H ₂ O			CO ₂ + H ₂ O + UV		
	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)
O-Ti	529.4	1.1	73.2	529.3	1.1	60.8	529.3	1.1	64.5
O _B	530.1	1.0	23.1	530.1	1.0	27.9	530.1	1.0	24.5
O _H	531.2	1.0	3.1	531.1	1.1	5.4	531.0	1.1	4.8
C-O*	-	-	-	532.3	1.1	3.0	532.1	1.0	2.3
H ₂ O _{phys.}	532.6	1.1	0.6	533.4	1.1	2.9	533.2	1.1	2.6
CH ₃ OH/CO _(g)	-	-	-	-	-	-	536.1	1.1	1.3

Table S9. Compilation of $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ NMR assignments. Superscripts on chemical shifts refer to the reported literature that can be found in the References Section (Supporting Information).

Functional Group	δ (ppm) ^{Reference}	Source/Type
Carbonate (CO_3^{2-})	169.9[106] 170.5[7] 171.1[107] 171.2[108] 171.0[109]	<i>Aragonite (CaCO₃)</i>
	(167.4-167.9)[106] 168.7[110] 168.2[7] 171.7[107] 168.8[108]	<i>Calcite (CaCO₃)</i>
	166.3[106] 167.9[7] 167.0[111] 169.5[112] 167.8[108] 170.0[111] 170.2[112] 169.0[113] 168.0[114] 168.2[115] 170.0[116] 166.5[117] 169.4[118]	<i>Amorphous or adsorbed CO₃²⁻</i>
	168.7[106] 170.1 - 169.1[7] 170.7 - 169.6[107]	<i>Vaterite (CaCO₃)</i>
	170.0[108]	<i>Witherite (CaCO₃)</i>
	167.2-167.5[106] 169.9[119] 169.9[108]	<i>Magnesite (MgCO₃)</i>
	169.3[120] (Zn ²⁺) (165.2-165.5)[121], 166.5[122] Ti ⁴⁺ _Bidentate	<i>Metal Coordinate Carbonate</i>
	171.1[7]	<i>monohydrocalcite (CaCO₃·H₂O)</i>
	167.9[7]	<i>Ikaite (CaCO₃·6H₂O)</i>
Hydrated carbonates ($\text{CO}_3^{2-} \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$)	(165.2, 163.1)[108]	<i>Hydromagnesite</i>
	13.0[7] Hydrogencarbonate 14.0[109] (7.4, 14.1, 18.6)[110]	
	161.0[113,114] 160.8[115] 167.0[116] 166.1[123] (bidentate) 161.4[118] 166-168[118] (bounded to two metal sites) (160.5, 160.7)[124] 163.6[125] 161.1[122]	<i>Amorphous or adsorbed HCO₃⁻</i>

	161.9[7]	
	164.5[7] 160.0[107]	<i>NaHCO₃</i>
	165.4[119] 165.4[108]	<i>Nesquehonite, [Mg(OH)(HCO₃)·2H₂O]</i>
HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻	160.9 (pH7), 161.6 (pH9), 163.3 (pH10.7) 162.6 (pH7), 166.7 (pH10.2), 170.8 (pH>12)[126]	<i>pH dependent</i>
CH₃CHO	201.0[127] (carbonyl), 23.0[127] (methyl), 198.7, 28.8[128]	<i>Acetaldehyde</i>
Carboxylate O=C-O	171.0-174[129] (in different environments) 163-220[130] (carboxyl - carbonyl) 170[131] (bound carboxylate) 178[131] (dangling carboxylate)	<i>RCHO₂⁻</i>
	161[127] (mobile formic acid) 165[127] 161.2[128] 171.3[124] 170.0[132] (Ti-O-CHO)	<i>Formate CHO₂⁻</i>
	176[127] 186[127] (strongly bonded to Ti) (171.2, 19.2)[128]	<i>Acetate CH₃CO₂⁻</i>
	169[131], 169.5[133] (bidentate) 174.1[118] (free) 170.1-178[131] (monodentate) 163.5[131] (bridge)	<i>Oxalate (COO)₂²⁻</i>
Methylene (CH₃)	62.0, 70.0[128] 3.3[134]	
Ester (O=C-O-R)	183.0[132]	
Ketones RC(=O)R	210.0[132]	
Orthocarbonate (C(OR)₄)	126.0[132] 120.0[135]	<i>Tetracoordinate alkyl</i>
Peroxo carbonate (HCO₄⁻)	(158.9, 159.0)[124] 161.7[125] 166.5[126] 158.9[136]	
Carbonyl (CO)	173-183[122] (backbone and side)	
Methoxyde (CH₃O⁻)	49.0[137] 49.3[138] 4.8[134]	
CH₂-O (H)	223.8[139]	
Hydroxyl (OH)	1.5-2.4[7] 0-1[140] 0-2[110] 1.8[141] 2.3[142]	<i>Terminal (OH_T)</i>
	7.3[141]	<i>Bridging (OH_B)</i>

	6.7[142]	
Water (H₂O)	5.0-5.6[7] 5.2[109] 4.8-6.0[110] 6.9[141] (interacting with OH _B)	
Peroxide (O-O)	11.1[143] 11.0[144]	

Table S10. NAP-XPS C 1s data collected on TiO₂ sample after reaction.

Component	UHV		
	BE (eV)	FWMH	C (%)
C-H	282.9	1.3	10.2
C-C	284.1	1.3	38.9
C-O	285.2	1.3	16.4
COO ⁻	286.8	1.3	4.2
HCO ₃ ⁻	287.9	1.3	18.3
CO ₃ ²⁻	289.0	1.3	12.0

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